

Chitosan Scaffold for the Culturing of Monocyte Cells

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Abstract:

Cell based assays have been the significant pillar for a large number of drug discovery process and tissue engineering experimentations. Cells naturally live in 3D microenvironments, while common laboratory tests and evaluations are routinely performed in 2D platforms. Hence, it becomes a necessity to study the cell in its native microenvironment to evaluate the efficacy of any drugs.

A three dimensional scaffold was prepared of chitosan solution, lyophilized and cross-linked to achieve desirable porous morphology. Characterization of surface morphology and pores of scaffold was performed by SEM. The swelling ratio of scaffolds in complete media was retrieved. Contact angle measurement was carried out for hydrophilicity determination. The in vitro degradation pattern of chitosan scaffold was evaluated upon treatment with Lysozyme enzyme. The selected scaffolds were further utilized for culturing of monocytes. The viability and morphology of the cells were evaluated.

Cross-linking of chitosan scaffold resulted in reduction of the no: of pores and directly proportionated with the swelling. Cross-linking was observed to be reversely proportional to hydrophilicity and degree of degradation. The 3D cultured monocytes were found to be viable and provides a key tool to assess the potential efficacy of new compounds in drug discovery.

Keywords:

3D culturing, Chitosan Scaffold, Crosslinking .

Induction Of Callus, Shoot Regeneration And Complete Plant Establishment From Leaf Sheath Explants Of *Kaempferia Galangal L* - An Important Medicinal Plant

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Abstract:

Kaempferia galanga Linn. of Zingiberaceae is a rhizomatous handsome herb is used extensively as a spice throughout tropical Asia and has a long history of medicinal use. It is a reputed remedy for cough, bronchitis and asthma, pectoral affections, dyspepsia, headache and malaria. skin diseases, wounds and spleen disorders and festering tumours. Rhizomes posses strong antimicrobial ,antioxidant, antitumor ,anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, insecticidal activity and also used for the treatment of hypertention. The present study describes a protocol for in vitro callus induction and plant regeneration from leaf sheath explants of *K. galanga* using Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium. For induction of callus, leaf sheath explants were cultured on MS medium supplemented with 2,4-D 2.0 mg/l + BAP 1.0 mg/l. Within 15 days yellow green friable or semi friable callus was observed. For shoot induction and multiplication yellow green friable or semi friable callus was transferred on to MS medium supplemented with different concentrations of BAP/KN (0.5-3.0 mg/l) alone or combination of NAA. Adventitious shoot buds were observed from the surface of the callus within 10 -20 days .The highest regeneration frequency (88.5%) with maximum number of shoots (13.16±1.18) was observed on 1.5 mg/l BAP with combination of 1.0 mg/l NAA. Elongation of shoots was observed on MS medium fortified with GA3 1.0 mg/l + BAP 1.5 mg/l, after 20 days. Rooting of in vitro shoots on half strength MS medium containing NA 1.0 mg/l. The healthy in vitro rooted plants acclimatized to green house conditions with river sand, garden soil and farmyard manure in the ratio of 1:2:1. Well developed plantlets transferred to normal climate, after 6 weeks. This protocol proves its utility for rapid propagation of *K.galangal* to be exploited for pharmaceutical and commercial purposes.

Keywords:

Kaempferia galanga , Leaf sheath ,callus culture.

Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles and pharmacognostic profile of the endemic *Cynometra beddomei* in Western Ghats

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Abstract:

Cynometra beddomei, a member of family Fabaceae used in traditional medicinal practices can be well exploited for various pharmacognostical studies. Narrow distribution and destruction of natural habitats make the plant less available for detailed phytochemical or pharmacological screening. The leaves of *Cynometra beddomei* is an important traditional medicine for piles and paralysis treatment. The present study deals with the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles and pharmacognostical profile of *Cynometra beddomei*. Qualitative analysis of *Cynometra beddomei* prain reflects the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, anthraquinones, Tannins, Phenolics, Carbohydrates, Sterols, Saponins, and glycosides. The nanoparticles were characterized by UV-visible spectrophotometer, FTIR and SEM. In UV spectrum analysis maximum absorption occur at 420nm. The absorption bands corresponding to O-H stretches, C=C stretches, C-N stretches and C-H bending were observed. Other minor bands were also observed. SEM analysis revealed the size of silver nanoparticles to be ranging from 200-250nm. In antibacterial and antifungal screening silver nanoparticle extract of leaves showed significantly higher activity compared to other extracts of plant. Antibacterial and antifungal activities were tested in different extracts. The methanol leaf extract showed higher ABTS and DPPH radical scavenging activity compared to chloroform and Ethyl acetate extracts of the plant. In cytotoxic activity, the chloroform leaf extract showed the higher percentage mortality compared to methanol and ethyl acetate extracts of the plant. LC50 values ranged from 0.61-10.33 μ g/ml, silver nanoparticles showed high cytotoxic effect when compared to other extracts. The present study offers a new platform for green nanotechnology with a cost effective, ecofriendly and sustainable approach.

Biological fixation and solubilization of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium by bacterial consortium SMCNPK18.

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Abstract:

The objectives of this study were to isolate, select, and identify nodulating bacteria from soil and develop a consortium that could perform biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) and solubilization of Phosphorus and Potassium. The bacteria were isolated from soil after which the screening for desired activity was done. Isolates with maximum activity were selected and developed bacterial consortium. Components of this consortium were analysed for its compatibility and combination was formulated. After the formulation this consortium were checked for its activity in situ and ex situ upon cucumber plants. When compared with untreated plants, the treated plants possessed 70% more activity. Hence it was prove that the bacterial consortium could efficiently enhance soil fertility.

Keywords:

Soil fertility, Microbial mediated fertility enhancement, Nitrogen fixation, Potassium solubilisation.

Gene expression and characterization of ATP1A1 exon17 gene by molecular approaches in Indian goats breed.

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Abstract:

The investigation was carried out to analyse the genetic polymorphism and gene expression of ATP1A1 gene in four different Indian goat breeds by using high resolution melting (HRM) and Real Time-PCR. ATPase is electro-genic ion pump which is maintains the balance of sodium and potassium ions in animal cells. The transport of Na⁺ & K⁺ is variable at cellular level during extreme hot period. Therefore, susceptible and tolerant animals were selected based on the physiological responses during hot period. Blood samples were collected from individuals, DNA was isolated. The 300 bp fragment of ATP1A1 gene was amplified by PCR and HRM genotyping was performed. The melting curves were analysed, differential temperature-shift plot showed three different genotypes in all the analysed samples. Out of the 135 samples, the distribution percentages were 55.56% (AA/Blue), 33.33% (AC/Red) and 11.11 % (CC/Green). The sequence variation revealed a SNP at 143rd position (A>C). The nucleotide diversity was 0.695±0.403, 0.732±0.424, 0.662±0.433 and 0.687±0.398 in Barbari, Jamunapari, Jakharna and Sirohi, respectively. The respiration rate (RR) was significantly different (P<0.05) between AA and AC (t=1.875, df=38) genotype and heart rate (HR) was significantly different (P<0.05) between AA and CC genotype. The relative expression pattern of ATP1A1 in SNP variants and non-variants animal tissues showed 19.09 and 6.93 fold higher than control (non-variant), respectively. Jamunapari showed higher fold value of ATP1A1 gene in comparison to Barbari, Jakharna and Sirohi. However, the heat stress-susceptible phenotype had significantly higher gene expression than stress-tolerant in all the breeds. The variation may be used as a marker for selection on the basis of physiological parameters and expression of ATP1A1 gene in goats indicating the specificity of expression in each tissue.

Keywords:

ATP1A1 gene, Physiological responses, PCR-HRM, RT-PCR, Indian goat

Phytochemical Investigation & Evaluation Of Anti-Hyperglycaemic Activity Of Different Extracts On Pereskia Bleo

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Abstract:

Diabetes has become a serious threat to mankind health due to severe long term health complications associated with it. Many medicinal plants have been reported to be useful in diabetes with more efficacies and less side effect compare to synthetic drugs. However, there is no conclusive research had been reported on the potential effects of active constituent of Pereskia bleo in treatment of diabetes. Aim is to study and evaluate the effect of antidiabetic activity of Pereskia bleo in Alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol extracts of Pereskia bleo were screened for the presence of anti-hyperglycaemic activity. Alloxan monohydrate was injected into rats by intraperitoneally with a single dose of 140 mg/kg for diabetes induction. 100 mg/kg of Metformin was chosen as a standard drug while both chloroform and methanol extracts with dose of 500 mg/kg/day were chosen for extract treated groups. The study was carried out for 5 days and the body weight and blood glucose level were measured on Day 1, Day 3 and Day 5. The results were analysed by using one way ANOVA test, Turkey T-test to find significant of study. The preliminary phytochemical analysis in both chloroform and methanol extracts revealed the presence of phytosterols, alkaloids, tannins, phenolic compounds and glycosides as the possible biologically active principles. Both chloroform and methanol extracts showed significant difference in reduction of blood glucose level compared to diabetic control group ($p < 0.05$). Maximum reduction in blood glucose level was shown by the Metformin with a percentage variation of 25.88%, followed by methanol extract with a percentage variation of 12.23% and the last chloroform extract with a percentage variation of 6.35%. Methanol extract of Pereskia bleo showed higher anti-hyperglycaemic effect in comparison to chloroform extract. This might be achieved by improving insulin resistance, inhibiting or delaying glucose absorption and suppressing hepatic glucose production. However, further studies shall be conducted to find out the exact mechanism of the extracts and further isolation of active constituents by column chromatography. This shall lead to possibilities of the future drug development for diabetes mellitus.

Keywords:

Diabetes mellitus, Pereskia bleo, Blood glucose